

Comparative Study on Sedative and Hypnotic Effects of Crude and Parched Semen *Ziziphi spinosae*: Integration of Network Pharmacology and *In vivo* Pharmacological Evaluation

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Abstract

Objective: To investigate the medicinal properties of SZS before and after processing and provide novel insights into its potential for treating insomnia.

Methods: The study employed the network pharmacology platform to gather information on the chemical composition of SZS, human targets, genes, molecular networks, and pathways associated with insomnia treatment using SZS. Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) was utilized to analyze the chemical profiles of crude SZS, parched SZS, and their combined decoction. The effects of different SZS products on p-chlorophenylalanine-induced insomnia mice were evaluated through pentobarbital-induced sleep tests, behavioral analyses, examination of brain tissue-related mRNA levels, and measurement of plasma neurotransmitters, aiming to explore the sedative and hypnotic effects of various SZS products.

Results: SZS was found to contain a total of 47 genes, including 22 target genes associated with insomnia. These genes may contribute to the sedative and hypnotic effects through 9 related pathways and 69 biological processes. The active components of SZS remained consistent before and after processing. Jujuboside B was found in higher concentrations in crude SZS, while jujuboside A was more abundant in parched SZS. Additionally, SZS exhibited reduced locomotor activity in mice, enhanced the hypnotic effect of pentobarbital sodium, and decreased the levels of acetylcholinesterase, α -1B adrenergic receptor, and solute carrier family 6 member 4 mRNA in the cortex and hippocampus of mice. The levels of acetylcholine, choline acetyltransferase, 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid, and glutamate in plasma increased, with the hypnotic effect being proportional to the dosage of the drug.

Conclusion: SZS demonstrates sedative and hypnotic effects, potentially mediated by its influence on neurotransmitter levels and related receptors within the central nervous system. There was a slight variation in regulatory capabilities before and after SZS processing, with the combined decoction of crude and parched SZS exhibiting a more pronounced effect, particularly at higher dosages.

Keywords: Semen *Ziziphi spinosae*; Processing; Network pharmacology; Insomnia; Sedation and hypnosis

Introduction

Insomnia is a common sleep disorder characterized by long-term difficulty in falling asleep, frequent waking-up at night, restless sleep, and daytime sleepiness and/or accompanied by early awakening, resulting in unsatisfactory sleep quality in over 10% of the world's adults. Long-term insomnia can lead to anxiety or depression, and increase the risk of high blood pressure, cardiovascular disease, Alzheimer's disease and other mental disorders, which becomes a heavy public health burden. Pharmacological therapy is the most important method to relieve insomnia, sedative and hypnotics including barbiturates, benzodiazepines and melatonin. Lately, melatonin receptor agonist ramelteon, orexin receptor antagonist suvorexant, and the antidepressant doxepin were also used for insomnia therapy. However, they tend to reduce the life quality of patients by the side-effects such as memory impairment, residual sedation, mental abnormality and drug dependence. As a great treasure house, traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) has obvious advantages in the prevention and treatment of diseases. Studies have shown that, compared with commonly used western medicines, TCM shows stable efficacy and fewer adverse reactions in the treatment of insomnia, which has drawn more and more attention in clinic and research [1].

Semen *Ziziphi spinosae* (SZS, Suanzaoren in Chinese), the dried

mature seed of *Ziziphus jujuba* Mill. var. *spinosae* (Bunge) Hu ex H. F. Chou, is a commonly used TCM for the treatment of insomnia. Modern pharmacological studies found the main effective components of SZS were saponins, flavonoids, fatty oil, etc., which was characterized by increasing the total amount of sleep and regulating the content of neurotransmitters such as 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT) and Dopamine (DA), thus inhibiting the central nervous system and producing sedative, hypnotic and anticonvulsant effects. In addition, SZS was also reported to have the effects of anti-hypertension, antiarrhythmia, antioxidation and immunoenhancement [2]. Interestingly, according to the classic processing theory of TCM, seed drugs should be parched before use

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so as to change properties and enhance efficacy. Clinical practice and pharmacological experimental studies further explored the sedative and hypnotic effects of crude and parched SZS products, both of which showed sedative and hypnotic effects in mice experiment. Compared with the single application, the combination of crude and parched SZS produced more obvious antidepressant activity which may be related to the inhibition of DA reuptake in some brain regions of mice and the increase of DA content in synapses. It was found that the contents of spiroxol, jujuboside A and B in the combined decoction of crude and parched SZS were higher than those in the single decoction of crude or parched product. However, the comprehensive mechanism of crude and parched SZS on sedation and hypnosis remains to be further clarified [3].

As a comprehensive and unique medical system, the characteristics of multi-component, multi-target and multi-channel action of TCM make it unable to understand herbal formulae at the molecular level by the traditional "one-drug, one-target" paradigm. Given the rapid progress in bioinformatics and systems biology, network pharmacology has become a booming field of modern research of TCM. It is a promising approach to find the relationship between disease targets and chemical components, establish the relationship network between drugs, pathways and diseases, and systematically analyze the potential action mechanism of TCM. The network analysis and *in vivo* study are frequently combined to directly verify the prediction results of network pharmacology, or discover potential effective substances in TCM, which has been applied to explore new pharmacologic effects of SZS, as well as potential active constituents and their mechanisms. The combination of serum chemistry with network pharmacology revealed that including ziyphusine, spinosin, apigenin, jujuboside A and coclaurine might serve as the material basis for SZS [4].

In this experiment, the potential effective components, pathways and targets of SZS in the treatment of insomnia were screened by network pharmacology, and the network mapping was combined with experimental research. The chemical profile of crude SZS (cSZS), parched SZS (pSZS) and their combination (c&pSZS) were detected by liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). And the different effects of cSZS, pSZS and c&pSZS were compared by pentobarbital sleep latency and spontaneous activity in different time periods. Then real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction (Real-time PCR) and LC-MS/MS techniques were used to detect the effects of three products of SZS on potential target genes and related neurotransmitters. The sedative and hypnotic effects of crude and parched SZS were compared from two aspects, which provide a new idea for the medicinal evaluation of SZS on insomnia treatment [5].

Materials and Methods

Prediction of potential effects of SZS on insomnia based on network pharmacology

Firstly, the SZS component-target network was established through the TCM system pharmacology database and analysis platform (TCMSP, <http://lsp.nwu.edu.cn/>). The compound data of all chemical components of SZS were collected, and the compounds meeting the two conditions of oral bioavailability (OB) $\geq 30\%$ and drug-like index (Drug Likeness, DL) ≥ 0.18 were selected for analysis and comparison. The SZS component-target network was established by using Cytoscape3.7.0 software.

Secondly, the target-target interaction network was established. The target genes associated with insomnia and sleep disorders were obtained from the human genetic database GeneCards (<http://www.genecards>).

org/) searching with the keywords "insomnia" and "sleep disorder" respectively. STRING database, a tool for searching interaction genes was used to find protein-protein interaction network (PPI network) data with species limited to *Homo sapiens* and confidence score > 0.4 . The first 10 target genes with high connection level were selected as the central genes, and the first three target genes were selected for follow-up experiments. Finally, the drug components were enriched and analyzed by Gene Ontology (GO) and Kyoto Encyclopaedia of Gene and Genome (KEGG). ClueGo was applied to GO and KEGG enrichment analysis, only the biological process and enrichment pathway with $p < 0.05$ were considered [6].

Materials and reagents

Crude Semen *Ziziphi Spinosae* (Bozhou Yonggang Pharmaceutical Factory Co., Ltd., Anhui, China); escitalopram oxalate (EO) tablets (Xi'an Janssen Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd., Shanxi, China); pentobarbital sodium (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany); para-chlorophenylalanine (PCPA, Sigma, St. Louis, Missouri, USA). RevertAid First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, Massachusetts, USA); KAPA SYBR FAST qPCR Master Mix (2x) (Kapabiosystems, Wilmington, Massachusetts, USA); primer (Beijing Jingke Xinye Biotechnology Co., Ltd., Beijing, China). acetylcholine (ACH), choline acetyl transferase (ChAT), epinephrine (E), norepinephrine (NE), glutamate (GLU), dopamine (DA), 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid (5-HIAA), 3, 4-dihydroxybenzylamine (DHBA, internal standard) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Formic acid, methanol and acetonitrile (chromatographic purity, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) and ultrapure water (Milli-Q water purifier, Millipore, MA, USA) [7].

Preparation of extract

The cSZS used in this study was authenticated and processed by Professor Guangzhong Wang of Hubei University of Chinese Medicine. cSZS (300 g), pSZS (300 g) and c&pSZS (150 g of cSZS and 150 g of pSZS) were decocted in water for 3 hours, respectively. The extracted solution was filtered, concentrated in vacuum with evaporator, then freeze-dried and stored at 4°C. The extraction rate of dry extract is about 16.7%. The lyophilized powder of cSZS, pSZS and c&pSZS were reconstituted in 50% methanol by ultrasonic extraction for 30 minutes at a concentration of 50 mg/ml and filtered through the 0.2 μm polytetrafluoroethylene filter prior to LC-MS/MS analysis [8].

Animal

In the experiment, 254 male Kunming mice weighing 18-22 g were purchased from Liaoning Experimental Animal Resource Center. Animals drink and eat freely in a constant temperature of $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $50 \pm 5\%$ humidity in a 12-hour light/dark cycle for 7 days before the experiment. All animal experiments are conducted in accordance with the guidelines of the Experimental Animal Ethics Committee in Hubei University of Chinese Medicine.

Drug administration and experimental group

The mice were divided into 9 groups ($n = 26$): control group (ultrapure water), model group (ultrapure water), EO group (1.3 mg/kg/day), the low dose of cSZS group (cSZS-l, 4.85 g/kg/day), the low dose of pSZS group (pSZS-l, 4.85 g/kg/day), the low dose of c&pSZS group (c&pSZS-l, 4.85 g/kg/day), the high dose of cSZS group (cSZS-h, 14.55 g/kg/day), the high dose of pSZS group (pSZS-h, 14.55 g/kg/day) and the high dose of c&pSZS group (c&pSZS-h, 14.55 g/kg/day). All drug solutions were given orally between 09:00 and 11:00 once a day for 7 consecutive days. Except for the control group, PCPA (200

mg/kg/day) was injected subcutaneously in other groups two days before the last administration. On the 7th day of the experiment, some mice conducted autonomous activity test within 24 hours after administration. After the test, the mice were killed immediately, plasma and brain tissue were collected and frozen at -80°C ($n=6/\text{group}$). Some mice were intraperitoneally injected 0.15% pentobarbital sodium 45 minutes after administration, and the drug activity was evaluated at the subthreshold hypnotic dose ($n=10/\text{group}$) and the suprathreshold hypnotic dose ($n=10/\text{group}$) [9].

Chemical profile of crude SZS, parched SZS and their combination

The methanol extract of cSZS, pSZS and c&pSZS was analyzed to compare their difference of chemical composition by Agilent 6420 Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, CA, USA) with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source. Chromatographic separation was achieved on an Agilent Eclipse plus RRHD C18 column ($100\times 2.1\text{mm I.D.}$, $1.8\ \mu\text{m}$) at 35°C , and the eluent was acetonitrile (A)-aqueous formic acid (100:0.1, v/v) (B) at a flow rate of $0.3\ \text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The injection volume was $2\ \mu\text{L}$. The gradient elution was performed as follows: 20–35% A at 0–10 min, 35–50% A at 10–18 min, 50–100% A at 18–19 min. Multiple reaction monitoring. Capillary voltages were 3500 V/–4000 V. Drying gas temperature was set at 350°C with a velocity of $9\ \text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and nebulizer pressure at 35 psi [10].

Pentobarbital induced sleep test

Before the beginning of the experiment, the blank mice of the same batch were used to explore the suprathreshold ($n = 10$) and subthreshold ($n = 10$) doses of pentobarbital sodium. The subthreshold hypnotic dose was $37.5\ \text{mg/kg}$ and the suprathreshold hypnotic dose was $46.5\ \text{mg/kg}$. After administration of pentobarbital sodium, the sleep condition of individual mice was observed: the disappearance of righting reflex within 1 minute was recorded as sleep, the time of disappearance of righting reflex was recorded as sleep latency, the time from falling asleep to righting reflex recovery was recorded as sleep duration, and the time from righting reflex recovery to the beginning of movement was recorded as movement convalescence time. When the mice failed to induce sleep in the 15 min after receiving pentobarbital sodium injection, the experimental results were recorded as follows: sleep latency of 15 minutes, sleep duration of 0 minutes, and exercise recovery time of 0 minutes. The incidence of sleep was calculated as follows: sleep incidence (%) = (number of falling asleep / total) \times 100 [11].

Autonomous activity test

Autonomous activity video analysis system (model: DB018, Shanghai Ruanlong Science and Technology Development Co., Ltd.) was used to evaluate the exercise activity of mice. The mice were put into an autonomous activity box with 30 cm in length and width, and the activity was recorded every 3 hours (12:00, 15:00, 18:00, 21:00, 0:00, 3:00, 6:00, 9:00). After each adaptation for 60 s, the activity was observed for 90 s.

Determination of ACHE, ADRA1B and SLC6A4 in hippocampus and cortex by Real time-PCR

About 40 mg of mouse cortex was extracted in 1.5 mL EP tube and the total RNA was dissolved in $15\ \mu\text{L}$ ddH₂O with RNA extract. The content of RNA was detected by ultra-micro spectrophotometer (model: K5500 Plus, Beijing Kaiiao Science and Technology Development Co., Ltd.). According to the instructions of reverse transcription kit, cDNA was synthesized by gradient PCR (model: T100, American Bio-Rad

company). The Real time-PCR reaction was carried out according to the quantitative amplification reaction system of the qPCR Master Mix Kit. The Real time-PCR instrument (model: CFX96, Bio-Rad Co., Ltd.) was set up under the reaction conditions of 95°C , 3min, 95°C , 3s, 60°C , 30s, and the melting curve was drawn at $65\text{--}95^{\circ}\text{C}$. The absorbance values of β -actin, acetyl cholinesterase (ACHE), alpha-1B adrenergic receptor (ADRA1B) and solute carrier family 6 (neurotransmitter transporter, serotonin) member 4 (SLC6A4) were measured. ΔCt value and $2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}}$ were calculated for data analysis: $\Delta\text{Ct}=\text{Ct target gene}-\text{Ct internal reference gene}$, $\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}=\Delta\text{Ct administration group}-\Delta\text{Ct control group}$. The primer sequence can be found in (Table 1). About 30 mg was taken from hippocampus, and the detection method was the same as that of cortex [12].

Determination of ACH, ChAT, E, NE, GLU, DA and 5-HIAA in plasma by LC-MS/MS

Neurotransmitter levels in mouse plasma were determined by a previously reported method with some modification (Huang et al., 2014). Briefly, $100\ \mu\text{L}$ of plasma was mixed with $300\ \mu\text{L}$ ice cold methanol (0.1% formic acid) and vortex-mixed for 2 min, and then centrifuged at $9,000\ \text{g}$ for 10 min at 4°C . The supernatant was transferred for the assay. The sample was analyzed on an Agilent 1290 Infinity series connected to an Agilent 6420 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer equipped with an ESI ion source (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, United States). The analytes were separated on an Ultimate Polar RP UHPLC column ($2.1\ \text{mm}\times 100\ \text{mm}$, $1.8\ \mu\text{m}$, Welch Materials, Maryland, USA) at 30°C . The mobile phase consisting of 0.1% formic acid in water (Solvent A) and acetonitrile (Solvent B) was used with a gradient elution: 0–4 min, 2% B; 6 min, 80% B; 8–10 min, 90% B at a flow rate of $0.3\ \text{mL}/\text{min}$. The ESI conditions were set as following: gas temperature 350°C , gas flow $10\ \text{L}/\text{min}$, capillary 4000 V, and nebulizer pressure 30 psi. MS acquisition of Ach, Epi, and 5-HIAA was performed in electrospray positive ionization multiple reaction monitoring mode.

Data analysis

All data are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). SPSS Statistics 22.0 software was used to analyze single factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) and LSD / Dunnett's T3 was used to evaluate the inter-group statistics. The result is considered to be statistically significant if $p < 0.05$. And use GraphPad Prism 6.0 software to draw graphics [13].

Results

The network pharmacological analysis: The compounds from SZS were selected from the TCMSP database, and the active components were screened by DL and OB (DL ≥ 0.18 and OB $\geq 30\%$). According to the results of TCMSP database, 9 compounds were obtained, and 7 compounds of SZS were screened out. Forty-seven genes related to the chemical composition of SZS were collected from the above steps. A

Table 1: Determination of ACH, ChAT, E, NE, GLU, DA and 5-HIAA in plasma by LC-MS/MS.

Target gene	Primer Sequence(5' to3')	Length
β -actin	Forward: CCACCATGTACCCAGGCATT	189bp
	Reverse: CGGACTCATCGTACTCCTGC	
ACHE	Forward: TTATGCCACCAGAGCCAAG	181bp
	Reverse: CTGGGGTATGGTGTCCACAC	
ADRA1B	Forward: CAACCAGACCTCGAGCAACT	167bp
	Reverse: TGAAGTAGTTGGTGGGCGTC	
SLC6A4	Forward: CGTCACCTGCTGAGGAGTTT	168bp
	Reverse: CCACCTTGCCAGACGTTTTG	

total of 46 genes with duplicates and no corresponding proteins were searched and deleted in UniProt one by one. The component-target network corresponding to SZS was constructed by Cytoscape 3.7.0 software, and the target network with 38 nodes and 46 edges as shown by (Figure 1) was obtained.

The green inner circle is the corresponding component, and the blue outer circle is the corresponding target. The size of the node in the network is proportional to the degree of this node, that is, the more edges connected to this node, the greater its degree, the larger the node.

Using GeneCards database, we obtained 758 disease genes of "insomnia" and 3914 disease genes of "sleep disorder". When the score of STRING, selection combination is more than 0.4, the target-target interaction network with 22 nodes and 58 edges is obtained as shown below (Figure 2A). The core genes of PPI network are found by R language, and the first 20 genes are shown in (Figure 2B). The first 10 target genes with high connectivity were selected as central genes: ACHE, ADRA1B, SLC6A4, alpha-1A adrenergic receptor (ADRA1A), alpha-1D adrenergic receptor (ADRA1D), amine oxidase [flavin-containing] B (MAOB), solute carrier family 6 (neurotransmitter transporter, serotonin) member 3 (SLC6A3), muscarinic acetylcholine receptor M1 (CHRM1), dopamine D1 receptor (DRD1) and alpha-2A adrenergic receptor (ADRA2A).

Target-target interaction network the more edges connected to the

Figure 1: SZS component-target network diagram.

Figure 2: SZS- insomnia common target-target interaction network.

node, the greater the degree of the node. (B) PPI network core gene. Abscissa represents the degree value.

GO enrichment analysis consists of three parts: BP (biological process), CC (cell composition) and MF (molecular function). Fifty-two target genes were uploaded to the database for annotation by Cluego, and the information of GO and KEGG pathways were visually obtained, only considering the GO biological processes and pathways with $p < 0.05$ (Figure 3A). A total of 69 biological processes were obtained by GO analysis. The first ten biological processes are vascular processes in the circulatory system, regulation of tube size, regulation of tube diameter, regulation of vascular size, regulation of muscle contraction, regulation of vascular diameter, contraction of smooth muscle, internal components of presynaptic membrane, internal components of postsynaptic membrane and components of postsynaptic membrane [14].

Nine related pathways were identified by KEGG pathway analysis: calcium signaling pathway, saliva secretion, adrenergic signal transduction in cardiomyocytes, serotonergic synapses, cocaine addiction, amphetamine addiction, regulation of fat decomposition in adipocytes and renin secretion (Figure 3B).

Different colors represent different functional groups, the connections of nodes represent the common genes between functional groups, and the size of nodes indicates their importance. (B) KEGG pathway analysis diagram. Different colors represent different functional groups, the connections of nodes represent the common genes between pathways, and the size of nodes indicates their importance.

Chemical profile of crude SZS, parched SZS and their combination based on LC-MS/MS: Spinosin, jujuboside A and jujuboside B are proved to be the main sedative and hypnotic active components in SZS (J. Wang, 1989). The results of this experiment showed that the content of Jujuboside B in cSZS was higher than that in the other two groups ($P < 0.05$ or $P < 0.01$), and the content of Spinosin and Jujuboside A in pSZS was higher than that in the other two groups ($P < 0.01$), while the content of main components in c&pSZS was between cSZS and pSZS (Figure 4A). By comparing the LC-MS fingerprints of the extract of the three groups, the active components extracted by hot reflux extraction and cold extraction of the three decoctions remained basically unchanged, and the similarity of chromatographic fingerprints was more than 99%, which is consistent with the reported results (D.N. Wang, 2004). Some peak areas of pSZS decreased in different degrees and no new peaks appeared in the pSZS decoctions, indicating that some components changed after the process (Figure 4B). Contents of Spinosin, Jujuboside A and Jujuboside B in cSZS, pSZS and c&pSZS.

Figure 3: Enrichment analysis of GO and KEGG, common targets of SZS- insomnia.

Figure 4: Chemical profile of cSZS, pSZS and c&pSZS based on LC-MS/MS.

(B) Base peak ion diagram of positive and negative ions of water extract of cSZS, pSZS and c&pSZS. *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01 (n = 3) [15].

Effects of SZS combined with pentobarbital sodium on sleep in mice: After the subthreshold dose of pentobarbital (37.5mg/kg, i.p.) was given, the number of mice falling asleep and sleep time were calculated. Compared with other groups, the sleep rate of EO, c&pSZS-l and c&pSZS-h groups increased, with c&pSZS-h being the most significant, suggesting that the drug can cooperate with pentobarbital to play a sedative and hypnotic role, but the results showed no statistical difference (Table 2).

Each group was administrated orally for 7 days, and PCPA (200mg/kg/day, S.C.) was injected into mice in the last 2 days to establish the insomnia model. Then 0.15% pentobarbital (37.5 mg/kg, S.C.) was injected 45 minutes after the last administration to observe the sleep incidence, latency, duration and movement convalescence time of mice in each group. The numerical value is expressed as mean ± SD (n = 10).

Combined with the suprathreshold hypnotic dose of pentobarbital sodium (46.5 mg/kg, i.p.), as shown by (Table 3), all mice in the control group fell asleep. After insomnia induced by PCPA (200mg/kg), the sleeping rate of mice decreased significantly (P < 0.01). The sleeping rate of the drug group was significantly better than that of the model group, and was in direct proportion to the dosage. Compared with the model group, the sleep latency of mice in pSZS-h, c&pSZS-l, c&pSZS-h groups decreased significantly (P < 0.05), and the sleep duration in c&pSZS-l group prolonged significantly (P < 0.05). However, there was no significant difference between the treatment groups.

Each group was administrated orally for 7 days, and PCPA (200mg/kg/day, S.C.) was injected into mice in the last 2 days to establish the insomnia model. Then 0.15% pentobarbital (46.5 mg/kg, S.C.) was injected 45 minutes after the last administration to observe the sleep incidence, latency, duration and movement convalescence time of mice in each group. The numerical value is expressed as mean ± SD (n = 10). *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01 compared with the control group, #P < 0.05, ##P < 0.01 compared with the model group [16].

Effects of SZS on 24-hour spontaneous activity in mice: The spontaneous activities at 8 time points within 24 hours were detected to study the effect of drugs on the exercise of mice. (Figure 5) shows that the activity of mice during the day is higher than that at night, which may be related to the manual intervention during the day (Kon et al., 2014; Shi et al., 2019). However, after PCPA treatment, compared with the control group, the activity distance of mice increased significantly from 21 o'clock to the next day (P<0.05 or P<0.01), and the static duration decreased, especially at 9 o'clock (P<0.05). And the circadian rhythm fluctuation tends to be stable. The area under the line chart showed that the 24h activity distance of mice increased significantly (P<0.01), and the static duration decreased, but there was no statistical difference. After the drug treatment, the activity distance of the mice decreased, the static duration increased, and the difference with the control group decreased. The EO and c&pSZS-h groups had the best effect, but there was no significant difference compared with the model group.

Effect of SZS on 24-hour activity distance of mice. (B) Effect of SZS on 24-hour rest time of mice. Each group was administrated orally for 7 days, and PCPA (200mg/kg/day, S.C.) was injected into mice in the last 2 days to establish the insomnia model. Then observe the autonomous behavior of mice in each group at eight time points (12:00, 15:00, 18:00, 21:00, 0:00, 3:00, 6:00, 9:00) within 24 hours by the activity video analysis system. The numerical value is expressed as mean ± SD (n = 6). *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01 compared with the control group. #P < 0.05, ##P < 0.01 compared with the model group. ΔP < 0.05, ΔΔP < 0.01 compared with the EO group. aP < 0.05, aaP < 0.01 compared with the cSZS-l group. bP < 0.05, bbP < 0.01 compared with the pSZS-l group. cP < 0.05, ccP < 0.01 compared with the c&pSZS-l group.

Effects of SZS on the levels of ACHE, ADRA1B and SLC6A4 mRNA in cortex and hippocampus of mice: According to the network pharmacology target-target interaction network analysis, we selected the first three target genes with the highest correlation of SZS in sleep disorders for detection. As shown by (Figure 6), compared with the control group, after injection of PCPA, the levels of ACHE and ADRA1B

Table 2: Effects of SZS on the sleep incidence and duration of mice treated with a sub-hypnotic dose of pentobarbital (37.5mg/kg).

Group	Dose (mg/kg)	No. falling (asleep/total)	Rate of sleep onset (%)	Sleep duration (min)
Control	–	0/10	0	0
Model	PCPA 200	0/10	0	0
EO	PCPA 200 + EO 1.3	02-Oct	20	3.39 ± 8.58
cSZS-l	PCPA 200 + cSZS 4.85×10 ³	0/10	0	0
pSZS-l	PCPA 200 + pSZS 4.85×10 ³	0/10	0	0
c&pSZS-l	PCPA 200 + c&pSZS 4.85×10 ³	01-Oct	10	0.10 ± 0.32
cSZS-h	PCPA 200 + cSZS 14.55×10 ³	0/10	0	0
pSZS-h	PCPA 200 + pSZS 14.55×10 ³	0/10	0	0
c&pSZS-h	PCPA 200 + c&pSZS 14.55×10 ³	03-Oct	30	2.77 ± 5.22

Table 3: Effects of SZS on the sleep incidence and duration of mice treated with a sup-hypnotic dose of pentobarbital (46.5mg/kg).

Group	Dose (mg/kg)	No. falling (asleep/total)	Sleep latency	Sleep duration	Movement convalescence time(min)
			(min)	(min)	
Control	–	10-Oct	5.79 ± 3.49	41.73 ± 38.81	23.08 ± 13.04
Model	PCPA 200	0/10	15.00 ± 0.00**	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00**
EO	PCPA 200 + EO 1.3	05-Oct	11.12 ± 4.37	3.50 ± 4.37	13.98 ± 16.73
cSZS-l	PCPA 200 + cSZS 4.85×10 ³	02-Oct	13.70 ± 2.96**	3.80 ± 8.84	1.20 ± 2.54*
pSZS-l	PCPA 200 + pSZS 4.85×10 ³	07-Oct	10.59 ± 3.34	16.29 ± 19.43	9.67 ± 9.20
c&pSZS-l	PCPA 200 + c&pSZS 4.85×10 ³	07-Oct	9.94 ± 3.65#	11.61 ± 8.52#	8.84 ± 7.33
cSZS-h	PCPA 200 + cSZS 14.55×10 ³	03-Oct	12.60 ± 3.98*	5.65 ± 11.75	5.05 ± 8.87
pSZS-h	PCPA 200 + pSZS 14.55×10 ³	08-Oct	7.63 ± 4.14##	22.97 ± 25.30	11.52 ± 10.35
c&pSZS-h	PCPA 200 + c&pSZS 14.55×10 ³	07-Oct	7.54 ± 5.26#	35.15 ± 27.14	7.22 ± 6.03

Figure 5: Effect of SZS on 24-hour activity distance and rest time in mice.

Figure 6: Effects of SZS on the mRNA expression of ACHE, ADRA1B and SLC6A4 in PCPA mice.

mRNA in the cortex and hippocampus of mice decreased, and the levels of SLC6A4 mRNA increased, which is related to the changes in the content of serotonin in the brain that affect enzyme activity. After 7 days of SZS administration, the levels of ACHE, ADRA1B and SLC6A4 mRNA in the cortex and hippocampus of mice showed a downward trend compared with the model group. The drug effect was closely related to the dose, and the high dose was more obvious. Among them, the levels of SLC6A4 mRNA in the hippocampus of cszs-h, pszs-h and c&pszs-h groups decreased significantly ($P < 0.01$). The level of SLC6A4 mRNA in hippocampus of EO group was lower than that of model group ($P < 0.05$), but there was no significant effect on ACHE and ADRA1B genes [17].

Each group was administrated orally for 7 days, and PCPA (200mg/kg/day, S.C.) was injected into mice in the last 2 days to establish the insomnia model. Then the cortex and hippocampus were collected, and the contents of acetylcholinesterase (ACHE), α -1B adrenergic receptor (ADRA1B) and solute carrier family 6 member 4 (SLC6A4) mRNA in

the tissues were analyzed by Real time-PCR. The numerical value is expressed as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$ compared with the control group. # $P < 0.05$, ## $P < 0.01$ compared with the model group. $\Delta P < 0.05$, $\Delta\Delta P < 0.01$ compared with the EO group. a $P < 0.05$, aa $P < 0.01$ compared with the cSZS-l group. b $P < 0.05$, bb $P < 0.01$ compared with the pSZS-l group. c $P < 0.05$, cc $P < 0.01$ compared with the c&pSZS-l group.

Effects of SZS on the contents of neurotransmitters ACH, ChAT, E, NE, GLU, DA and 5-HIAA in plasma of mice: By analyzing the top 10 target genes with high connectivity in the development of sleep disorders, we found that neurotransmitter related proteins such as ACH, ChAT, E, NE, GLU, DA, 5-HIAA play an important role in regulating sleep behavior. PCPA is a highly selective inhibitor of tryptophan hydroxylase in the brain, which can block the biosynthesis of 5-HT in the brain. As the final product of 5-HT, 5-HIAA reflects the content and metabolism of 5-HT in the body. Compared with normal mice, the contents of ACH ($P < 0.01$), ChAT ($P < 0.05$), and 5-HIAA ($P < 0.05$) in

plasma of PCPA mice decreased, while the contents of E, NE ($P < 0.05$), GLU, and DA increased, which was consistent with the effect of insomnia model. After administration, SZS can increase the contents of ACH, Chat and 5-HIAA, indicating that SZS can improve the emptying of 5-HT by PCPA and has the protective effect of cholinergic system, which is consistent with the reported results. At the same time, the levels of E, NE and DA decreased, but the statistical results showed no significant difference. Interestingly, the plasma GLU content in SZS groups increased, suggesting that SZS can not only hypnotize and calm, but also may participate in the regulation of arousal level, and also play a role in restoring the biological clock rhythm of insomnia models. As a selective 5-HT reuptake inhibitor, EO showed that it could significantly increase the levels of ACH and 5-HIAA ($P < 0.05$ or $P < 0.01$).

Each group was administrated orally for 7 days, and PCPA (200mg/kg/day, S.C.) was injected into mice in the last 2 days to establish the insomnia model. Then the plasma was collected and the contents of acetylcholine (ACH), choline acetyl transferase(ChAT), epinephrine (E), norepinephrine(NE), glutamate(GLU), dopamine(DA), 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid (5-HIAA) in the plasma were analyzed by LC-MS/MS. The numerical value is expressed as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$ compared with the control group. # $P < 0.05$, ## $P < 0.01$ compared with the model group. $\Delta P < 0.05$, $\Delta\Delta P < 0.01$ compared with the EO group. a $P < 0.05$, aa $P < 0.01$ compared with the cSZS-I group. b $P < 0.05$, bb $P < 0.01$ compared with the pSZS-I group. c $P < 0.05$, cc $P < 0.01$ compared with the c&pSZS-I group.

Each group was administrated orally for 7 days, and PCPA (200mg/kg/day, S.C.) was injected into mice in the last 2 days to establish the insomnia model. Then the plasma was collected and the contents of acetylcholine (ACH), choline acetyl transferase(ChAT), epinephrine (E), norepinephrine(NE), glutamate(GLU), dopamine(DA), 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid (5-HIAA) in the plasma were analyzed by LC-MS/MS. The numerical value is expressed as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$ compared with the control group. # $P < 0.05$, ## $P < 0.01$ compared with the model group. $\Delta P < 0.05$, $\Delta\Delta P < 0.01$ compared with the EO group. a $P < 0.05$, aa $P < 0.01$ compared with the cSZS-I group. b $P < 0.05$, bb $P < 0.01$ compared with the pSZS-I group. c $P < 0.05$, cc $P < 0.01$ compared with the c&pSZS-I group [18].

Discussion

In the long-term practice of TCM, SZS has been proved to have sedative and hypnotic effects which are increased after parching and processing. Although the chemical composition of SZS has been widely studied, the differences between the active components and related mechanisms before and after SZS frying are far from clear.

We have previously reported that SZS has effects on spontaneous activity, sleep and convulsions of model organisms. In this study, a variety of target genes and typical pathways closely related to SZS were found through the methods of network pharmacology. It is concluded that SZS regulates insomnia mainly by target genes like ACHE, ADRA1B, SLC6A4, ADRA1A, ADRA1D and biology process as well as pathway of regulating cholinergic system, adrenergic system (Figures 1-3):ACHE is an enzyme involved in the hydrolysis of ACH and important neurotransmitter in the central cholinergic system. Studies have shown that ACHE stimulation can lead to the decrease of ACH in the synaptic cleft, resulting in a decrease in cholinergic activity. The role of cholinergic system in the generation and maintenance of REM sleep has been determined, and the relationship between cholinergic system, electrophysiological rhythm, circadian rhythm and temperature has been demonstrated in multi-parameter measurements in free-moving rats. The widely projected adrenergic system of the central nervous

system may play an important role in sleep/wake regulation. As a subtype of adrenergic receptors, ADRA1B mediates the effects of many natural catecholamines, epinephrine and norepinephrine, and its over activity can lead to neurodegeneration and pro-depressant phenotype. ADRA1A acts an important part in the regulation of learning and memory, and is positively correlated with enhanced synaptic plasticity, antidepressant-like behavior and longevity. 5-HT is a kind of inhibitory neurotransmitter in the brain, which is involved in regulating the rhythm of central fatigue and sleep awakening. SLC6A4 gene is the coding gene of 5-HT transporter. 5-HT transporter can absorb the 5-HT of synaptic gap back into presynaptic membrane. The increase of 5-HT transporter can reduce the concentration of 5-HT in synaptic cleft, and then reduce the activity of 5-HT nervous system, leading to insomnia. On the contrary, reducing the expression of SLC6A4 gene can reduce the number of 5-HT transporters, thus enhance the effect of 5-HT, and then play the role of improving sleep. There are other related targets, such as monoamine oxidase, the main metabolic enzyme of monoamine neurotransmitters, SLC6A3, which mediates the active reuptake of DA by synapses, CHRM1 innervated by cholinergic neurons, DRD1, which mediates the release of DA, etc., all of which have been proved to be closely related to the nervous system and participate in sleep-awakening, learning and memory, attention, motor control and other functions [19].

To verify this result, we used LC-MS/MS technology to detect the content of sedative and hypnotic active ingredients in cSZS, pSZS and c&pSZS decoction (Figure 4). The results showed that the drug components did change after processing. The content of jujuboside B in cSZS was more than that in pSZS, and the content of jujuboside an increased after processing into pSZS, which may be an important reason for affecting the efficacy of the drug. After that, we carried out *in vivo* experiments to observe the effects of crude and parched SZS on the sleep behavior of PCPA-induced insomnia mice. PCPA is an inhibitor of 5-HT synthesis, which consumes almost 80% of the 5-HT content in the brain. Therefore, it is used in this experimental study to make sleep deprivation models. EO is a known selective 5-HT reuptake inhibitor used as a positive control. We observed the hypnotic effect of SZS on mice induced by pentobarbital sodium (Table 2, 3). Pentobarbital sodium can be used as a short-term sedative and hypnotic. It is one of the classic sleep evaluation experiments. In this study, when pentobarbital sodium was injected into mice, SZS increased the sleep incidence of sub threshold dose (37.5 mg/kg), significantly reduced the sleep latency and prolonged the sleep duration of mice treated with the suprathreshold dose (46.5 mg/kg). The effect of SZS-h was better than that of SZS-l, and the dose-effect relationship was proportional. Then, the effect of SZS on the motor activity of mice was studied using the autonomous activity video analysis system (Figure 5). 24-hour autonomous activity is usually used to evaluate animal activity detection and circadian rhythm, as well as sedation or anti-anxiety effects. The experiment confirmed that the circadian rhythm in normal mice changed more obviously. PCPA treatment eliminated the rhythmicity of mice and decreased the rest time, indicating the activity was more significant. SZS have a sedative effect on mice by reducing the exercise activity and increasing the rest time, but there is no significant difference. And then according to the cortex and hypothalamus of mice, Real-time PCR technique was used to verify the results of the first three targets related to SZS sleep disorder screened by network pharmacology (Figure 6). It was found that high dose of SZS had the best effect, and the levels of ACHE, ADRA1B and SLC6A4 mRNA in the cortex and hippocampus of mice were significantly lower than those in the control group or PCPA insomnia mice. In addition, it is interesting that some low dose groups have an increasing effect and the high and low dose groups of the

Figure 7: Effects of SZS on the contents of neurotransmitters ACH, ChAT, E, NE, GLU, DA and 5-HIAA in plasma of mice.

same product show the opposite phenomenon. For example, high dose pSZS can significantly reduce the content of ACHE mRNA in cortex and SLC6A4 mRNA in hippocampus, while low dose of pSZS increases the content of both, suggesting that the hypnotic effect of SZS may also be related to drug processing, administration dose, administration time and so on. Finally, LC-MS/MS was used to detect the target-related neurotransmitters in the plasma of mice (Figure 7). The results showed that SZS, especially high dose SZS, could increase the contents of ACH, ChAT and 5-HIAA in plasma, indicating that SZS could improve the emptying effect of PCPA on 5-HT, which was consistent with the results of Real-time PCR. In addition, SZS increases the plasma GLU content, which indicates that SZS may also participate in the regulation of arousal level and play a role in restoring the biological clock rhythm of insomnia models.

The innovation of this study lies in the combination of *in vivo* research and network pharmacology research, which provides a direction for multi-component/multi target research on sedative and hypnotic effects of SZS, as well as differences and influence mechanisms before and after processing of traditional Chinese medicine. In this study, network pharmacological analysis was used to explain the potential effective components and mechanisms of SZS in treating insomnia and sleep disorders, and it was verified by *in vivo* experiments based on theoretical predictions. It was found that there was no significant difference between cSZS, qSZS and c&qSZS mixture, but there was significant difference between high and low doses. The c&pSZS-h group (14.55g/kg/day) had the best effect. It can be seen that the sedative and hypnotic effects of SZS are not only related to the changes of active components before and after processing, but also related to the dosage and compatibility of drugs. However, the herbal medicine database is being further discovered and improved, whether other seed drugs have the same effect, and what is the mechanism leading to this change remains to be further studied and explored [20].

Conclusion

To sum up, SZS has a good hypnotic and sedative effect, and has a certain impact on the circadian rhythm. This effect may be caused by affecting the target gene levels of neurotransmitters such as ACHE, ADRA1B, SLC6A4 and their related receptors and mediating the central nervous system. The regulating ability of SZS was slightly different before and after processing, which was closely related to the

composition, dosage and compatibility of the drug and the effect of high dose c&qSZS was the best.

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Author Contributions

PW conceived and designed the experiment. JX, MC and LLC carried out experiments. BX and GJX analyzed the data. JX, MC and LLC wrote the paper. All the authors reviewed and approved the submitted version of the paper.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval to report this case was obtained from the Experimental Animal Ethics Committee in Hubei University of Chinese Medicine Review Board (HUCMS202011010), Hubei Province, China.

Statement of Human and Animal Rights

All of the experimental procedures involving animals were conducted in accordance with the Institutional Animal Care guidelines of Hubei University of Chinese Medicine and approved by the Experimental Animal Ethics Committee in Hubei University of Chinese Medicine Review Board, Hubei Province, China.

Statement of Informed Consent

There are no human subjects in this article and informed consent is not applicable.

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